

Postharvest Biology and Technology

POSTHARVEST UV-B AND UV-C RADIATION ENHANCED THE BIOSYNTHESIS OF GLUCOSINOLATES AND ISOTHIOCYANATES IN BRASSICACEAE SPROUTS

--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	
Article Type:	Research Paper
Keywords:	broccoli; radish; Crucifereae; fresh-cut; glucoraphanin; sulforaphane
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Abstract:	<p>The objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of UV lighting (UV-B, UV-C and UV-C + UV-B) as a postharvest abiotic stress in the quality changes of minimally processed Brassicaceae sprouts (broccoli and radish) during a shelf-life period of 10 d at 4 °C. No UV illumination was used as control (CTRL). The total UV-C doses received were 9 kJ m⁻² (UVC) and 15 kJ m⁻² UV-B (UVB) by applying the 50% of such doses after harvest and on the first day of the shelf-life. Results showed that when UVC was applied, the epiphytic microbial load was reduced up to 1 log CFU g⁻¹ fw. The UVB treatment reported the highest total phenolic content (TPC) and total antioxidant capacity (TAC) after 10 d at 4 °C. In general, both species showed an amelioration effect in the TPC and TAC after UV treatments, which also enhanced the glucosinolate (GL) and the main isothiocyanates (ITC) content. In fact, UVB increased by ~30 % the GL content compared to CTRL samples, which were mostly aliphatic GLs in radish and indolyl GLs in broccoli. As main ITC, sulforaphane content was enhanced by 37.5 % in UVB-treated broccoli sprouts while the sulforaphane content was highly increased by 72 % in radish sprouts. In conclusion, UVB radish sprouts reported 5-fold higher GL content and 60-fold higher biologically ITC content than broccoli sprouts. Therefore, its inclusion in the daily intake is recommended to increase the prevention of chronic inflammatory diseases.</p>
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February 22nd, 2021

Dear Editor:

I am pleased to submit our article '**POSTHARVEST UV-B AND UV-C RADIATION ENHANCED THE BIOSYNTHESIS OF GLUCOSINOLATES AND ISOTHIOCYANATES IN BRASSICACEAE SPROUTS**'. The authors Lorena Martínez-Zamora, Noelia Castillejo, and myself agree to its submission to the highly appreciated **Postharvest Biology and Technology** Journal. This work is an original research carried out by the authors. All authors agree with the contents of the manuscript and its submission to this Journal. All listed Authors have significantly contributed to the work and agree to be in the author list. No part of the research has been published in any form elsewhere.

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of UV lighting (UV-B, UV-C and UV-C + UV-B) as a postharvest abiotic stress in the quality changes of minimally processed *Brassicaceae* sprouts (broccoli and radish) during a shelf-life period of 10 days at 4 °C. The novelty of this work lies on UV-C and UV-B radiation hormesis in the biosynthesis of nutraceutical compounds while maintaining the optimum quality of broccoli and radish sprouts.

As main results, both species showed an amelioration effect in the TPC and TAC after UV treatments, which also enhanced the glucosinolate and the main isothiocyanates content. In fact, as main ITC, sulforaphane content was enhanced by 37.5 % in UVB-treated broccoli sprouts while the sulforaphane content was highly increased by 72 % in radish sprouts under the same treatment.

In conclusion, UVB radish sprouts reported 5-fold higher GL content and 60-fold higher biologically ITC content than broccoli sprouts. Therefore, its inclusion in the daily intake is recommended to increase the prevention of chronic inflammatory diseases.

Furthermore, the industrial relevance of the present study lies on the improvement of the nutritional quality of *Brassicaceae* sprouts under low doses of postharvest UV-C and UV-B lighting. Since the consumers demand for functional foods able to improve their health, especially during the pandemic caused by SARS-COV 2, food industry has focused on looking for new techniques to improve the biosynthesis of phytochemicals, such as glucosinolates and isothiocyanates.

We hope that you agree on the merits and appropriateness of this study for publication in this journal.

Looking forward to your comments, sincerely yours

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Postharvest UV-B and C increased the total phenolic content and antioxidant capacity
- UV-B increased by ~30 % the glucosinolate content in broccoli and radish sprouts
- Sulforaphane was enhanced by 37.5 % in UV-B-treated broccoli sprouts
- Sulforaphane was increased by 72 % in UV-B-treated radish sprouts
- UV-B treated radish sprouts reported 5-fold higher GL and 60-fold ITC content than broccoli

1 **POSTHARVEST UV-B AND UV-C RADIATION ENHANCED THE**
2 **BIOSYNTHESIS OF GLUCOSINOLATES AND**
3 **ISOTHIOCYANATES IN *BRASSICACEAE* SPROUTS**

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11 **ABSTRACT**

12 The objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of UV lighting (UV-B, UV-C and
13 UV-C + UV-B) as a postharvest abiotic stress in the quality changes of minimally
14 processed *Brassicaceae* sprouts (broccoli and radish) during a shelf-life period of 10 d at
15 4 °C. No UV illumination was used as control (CTRL). The total UV-C doses received
16 were 9 kJ m⁻² (UVC) and 15 kJ m⁻² UV-B (UVB) by applying the 50% of such doses after
17 harvest and on the first day of the shelf-life. Results showed that when UVC was applied,
18 the epiphytic microbial load was reduced up to 1 log CFU g⁻¹ fw. The UVB treatment
19 reported the highest total phenolic content (TPC) and total antioxidant capacity (TAC)
20 after 10 d at 4 °C. In general, both species showed an amelioration effect in the TPC and
21 TAC after UV treatments, which also enhanced the glucosinolate (GL) and the main
22 isothiocyanates (ITC) content. In fact, UVB increased by ~30 % the GL content compared
23 to CTRL samples, which were mostly aliphatic GLs in radish and indolyl GLs in broccoli.
24 As main ITC, sulforaphane content was enhanced by 37.5 % in UVB-treated broccoli
25 sprouts while the sulforaphane content was highly increased by 72 % in radish sprouts.
26 In conclusion, UVB radish sprouts reported 5-fold higher GL content and 60-fold higher
27 biologically ITC content than broccoli sprouts. Therefore, its inclusion in the daily intake
28 is recommended to increase the prevention of chronic inflammatory diseases.

29 **Keywords:** broccoli, radish, *Crucifereae*, fresh-cut, glucoraphanin, sulforaphane.

30 1. INTRODUCTION

31 Plants and vegetables are rich in phytonutrients and fibers, whose intake is necessary and
32 beneficial for the human health. Indeed, regular consumption of plant derivatives has been
33 associated with a reduced risk of chronic diseases, such as cancer, obesity, respiratory or
34 cardiovascular dysfunction (Boeing et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2014). For this reason, new
35 trends in agriculture and fruit and vegetables Industry have focused on the research of
36 new ways to increase the content of bioactive compounds in these ‘super foods’.

37 Cruciferae, like broccoli (*Brassica oleracea* var. *italica*) and radish (*Raphanus sativus*),
38 have become very important due to their high GL content (Raiola et al., 2018;
39 Soundararajan and Kim, 2018). As a matter of fact, GLs have been known by their cancer-
40 fighting properties (Raiola et al., 2018; Soundararajan and Kim, 2018) because GLs
41 synthesize isothiocyanates (ITC) by the enzyme myrosinase. One of the most important
42 ITC in the *Brassicaceae* is the sulforaphane in broccoli sprouts and the sulforaphene in
43 radish sprouts, with a double bond formation (Figure 1). However, it is not the only
44 product of hydrolysis in cruciferous species, since a high percentage is converted into
45 sulforaphane nitrile, being sulforaphane the biologically active product (Vanduchova et
46 al., 2019). In addition, activity of the epithiospecific protein (ESP) promotes the
47 formation of the non-bioactive compound sulforaphane nitrile (Castillejo et al., 2018) as
48 well as nitrile-specifier protein (NSP) (Wang et al., 2017). In addition, ITC and indolyl
49 compounds (hydrolytic products of GLs) by their positive role modulating cell cycles,
50 acting as anti-inflammatory compounds, and allowing the apoptosis of cancer cells
51 (Raiola et al., 2018; Soundararajan and Kim, 2018).

52

53 **Figure 1.** Conversion pathway of main glucosinolates to biologically active
 54 isothiocyanates in broccoli and radish sprouts.

55 From other point of view, sprouts and microgreens are gaining popularity as ‘the product
 56 obtained from the germination of seeds during the first steps of their development’
 57 (Benincasa et al., 2019). Moreover, the content of nutrients of sprouts are not only
 58 proteins, carbohydrates, fibers, vitamins, minerals. In fact, they are also rich in phenolic
 59 compounds, carotenoids, GLs, ITCs.

60 In this line of knowledge, the techniques used in the sector able to enhance these bioactive
 61 compounds have been widely investigated in recent years. Particularly, light is a key
 62 factor which directly affects to plant growth and synthesis of primary and secondary

63 metabolites, such as phenolic compounds, flavonoids, GLs, and sulforaphane, among
64 others (Zhang et al., 2020). In fact, photosynthesis can be adjusted by changes in the
65 wavelength, light intensity, and photoperiod of artificial light source applied. In this way,
66 UV lighting (200 – 400 nm) can induce the expression of antioxidant enzymes enhancing
67 the accumulation of anthocyanins, flavonoids, phenolic acids, GLs and ITCs (Dou et al.,
68 2019; Moreira-Rodríguez et al., 2017a; Schreiner et al., 2014).

69 In plants, UV RESPONSE LOCUS 8 (UVR8), as main UV-B receptors, are in charge to
70 regulate flavonoid biosynthesis, hypocotyl growth inhibition, and leaf cell expansion
71 (Jenkins, 2009). For that, although UV light has been considered harmful for
72 photosynthesis, moderate UV doses have shown amelioration effects on the biosynthesis
73 of several secondary metabolites, such as flavonoids with photoprotective activity (Guidi
74 et al., 2016). Thus, postharvest UV-B radiation (280 – 315 nm) has shown to improve the
75 GL content in broccoli microgreens (Lu et al., 2018) and broccoli florets (Formica-
76 Oliveira et al. 2017). Furthermore, although the use of UV-C (200 – 280 nm) has widely
77 shown a high germicidal effect for water treatment, air disinfection, surface
78 decontamination and vegetable preservation (Formica-Oliveira et al. 2017; Tomás-
79 Callejas et al., 2012), recent findings have also shown an enhancement in the biosynthesis
80 of carotenoids and phenolic compounds in tomatoes (Pataro et al., 2015) and
81 *Clerodendrum volubile* (Adetuyi et al., 2020) after low doses of postharvest UV-C
82 treatments. In this way, low doses of UV-C radiation have also shown to modulate the
83 biosynthesis of vitamin C and phenolic compounds in acerola fruit by increasing the
84 mitochondria activity and reactive oxygen species (ROS) production (Rabelo et al.,
85 2020). In addition, postharvest combination of UV-B and UV-C treatments have also
86 been studied in bimi broccoli (Formica-Oliveira et al. 2017) and peaches (Abdipour et al.,

87 2019) obtaining promising results. Nevertheless, the effect of this light combination has
88 never been simultaneously studied in any sprouts.

89 Therefore, considering the limited knowledge about the postharvest application of UV-B
90 and UV-C light on sprouts, the main objective of the present study was to elucidate the
91 effects of reduced doses of UV postharvest lighting in crucifers sprouts, both the single
92 and combined UV-C and UV-B, on quality preservation and on the main nutraceuticals
93 compounds during a shelf-life period as a minimally processed product.

94 **2. MATERIAL AND METHODS**

95 **2.1. Plant material and sprouting conditions**

96 Broccoli (*Brassica olearacea* var. *italica*) and radish (*Raphanus sativus*) seeds were
97 supplied by Intersemillas S.A. (Valencia, Spain). Four g of broccoli seeds and two g of
98 radish seeds were weighed and sanitized during 10 min with a fungicide (Geoxe 50 WG
99 - Fludioxonil 50 % w/w -; Syngenta). Afterwards, two rinses were conducted with
100 autoclaved distilled water and they were left immersed in water for 18 h in darkness. In a
101 laminar flow hood, the broccoli and radish seeds were arranged in polypropylene (PP)
102 baskets (170 x 120 x 50 mm), using a layer of filter paper moistened with sprayed
103 autoclaved distilled water as a support. To ensure a high relative humidity (RH) the trays
104 were covered with a 40 µm bioriented PP (OPP) film. Broccoli and radish seeds
105 germination was carried out in a growth chamber (Sanyo MLR-350 H, Japan) for 10 d at
106 20 °C and 90 % RH in darkness, until sprouts reached the morphological characteristics
107 described in Table 1.

108

109 **Table 1.** Morphological characteristics of broccoli and radish sprouts harvested after 10
 110 germination days at 20 °C and 90 % RH under Darkness conditions.

	Broccoli sprouts <i>Brassica olearacea var. italica</i>	Radish sprouts <i>Raphanus sativus</i>
Cotyledon (cm)	0.77 ± 0.02	
Hypocotyl (cm)	3.19 ± 0.08	
Diameter (cm)	0.09 ± 0.00	0.13 ± 0.00
Radical (cm)	2.75 ± 0.57	
FW/DW	7.6	5.8

111 The morphological characteristics were determined using the ImageJ program (Wayne Rasband, Maryland, USA).

112 n=30. FW/DW: Fresh weight/Dry weight ratio; n=70

113 **2.2. Minimal processing and postharvest UV treatments**

114 After 10 germination days at 20 °C, the sprouts were harvested and washed for 1 min with
 115 a sodium hypochlorite solution (150 ppm; 5 °C; pH=6.5) and then rinsed in water for 1
 116 min at 5 °C. A 2 min dewatering process on a paper filter sheet was accomplished. The
 117 minimally processed sprouts were kept for 10 d at 4 °C in 250 mL PP closed baskets (10
 118 x 8 x 3.5 cm) under 90-95 % RH and normal atmospheric gas partial pressures.

119 UVB and UVC treatments were applied twice: after harvesting (day 0) and after 24 h on
 120 the first day of the shelf-life period at 4 °C. UV treatments were carried out a reflective
 121 stainless-steel chamber as described by Formica-Oliveira et al. (2017b). The radiation
 122 chamber was equipped with 6 UV-B unfiltered emitting lamps (TL 40W/01 RS; Philips,
 123 Eindhoven, The Netherlands) and 6 UV-C unfiltered emitting lamps (TUV 36W/G36 T8;
 124 Philips, Eindhoven, The Netherlands). Broccoli and radish sprouts were placed between
 125 the two lines of lamps at 17.5 cm above and below. The applied UV-B intensity of 7.99
 126 ± 0.40 W m⁻² was calculated as the mean of 20 readings on each side of the net using a
 127 LP 471 UVB (Delta OHM, Italy) radiometer. The applied UV-C intensity of 26.06 ± 0.37
 128 W m⁻² was calculated as the mean of 20 readings on each side of the net using a VLX

129 254 (Vilber Lourmat, Marne la Vallee, France) radiometer. Packed sprouts were placed
130 between the two lines of lamps at 17.5 cm above and below. The light intensities were
131 kept constant, and the applied doses were varied by altering the exposure time at the fixed
132 distance. These doses were applied on day 0 and 1 after harvesting trying to adapt this
133 model to the industry, where sprouts are kept a short period of time before distribution
134 until the pathogenic microbial quality analysis are being conducted. The applied UV
135 treatments were as follows:

- 136 - **CTRL**: No UV radiation was used as control.
- 137 - **UVC**: the sprouts received a total effective dose of 9 kJ m^{-2} UV-C by means of 2
138 applications of $4.5 \text{ kJ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (2 min 34 s) after harvesting and after 24 h of the
139 postharvest refrigerated period.
- 140 - **UVB**: the sprouts received a total effective dose of 15 kJ m^{-2} UV-B by means of
141 2 applications of $7.5 \text{ kJ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (15 min 39 s) after harvesting and after 24 h of the
142 postharvest refrigerated period.
- 143 - **UVC+B**: the sprouts received the sum of both treatments with a total effective
144 dose of 9 kJ m^{-2} UV-C + 15 kJ m^{-2} UV-B by means of 2 applications of 4.5 kJ m^{-2}
145 d^{-1} UV-C and $7.5 \text{ kJ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ UV-B applied after harvesting and after 24 h of the
146 postharvest refrigerated period.

147 The total dose received was based on our previous unpublished trials and on those
148 recommended by Formica-Oliveira et al. (2017b) in order to obtain maximum
149 phytochemicals accumulation while minimizing heating and evaporation processes
150 during treatment, which may affect the quality of the product.

151 After 1 h of the UV application on days 0 and 1, and on the 4th, 7th, and 10th d of the shelf-
152 life period at 4 °C, samples were frozen at -80 °C until they were freeze-dried (Lyoquest-
153 85, Telstar Technologies, Terrassa, Spain) before the analytical determinations were

154 carried out. In the detailed sampling days, mesophilic, psychophilic, enterobacteria,
155 yeasts, and moulds growth were analysed following standard methods (Castillejo et al.,
156 2016; Martínez-Hernández et al., 2013). All microbial counts were reported as log colony
157 forming units per gram of product ($\log \text{CFU g}^{-1}$). Three repetitions per treatment were
158 analysed on each sampling day.

159 **2.3. Extraction of phenolic compounds**

160 Twenty-five mg of freeze-dried sprouts were placed in tubes and 3 mL MeOH:H₂O (80:20,
161 v/v) were added. The extraction was carried out in an orbital shaker (Stuart, Stone, UK)
162 where the samples were vigorously shaken for 1 h in darkness at 4 °C. The methanolic
163 extracts were centrifuged at 3220 g for 10 min at 4 °C. The supernatant was collected and
164 kept at -80 °C until analysis of Total Phenolic Content (TPC) and Total Antioxidant
165 Capacity (TAC).

166 **2.4. Total phenolic content**

167 TPC was determined as previously described by Castillejo et al. (2021). Briefly, 19 μL
168 sample extract were placed on a 96-well plate (Greiner Bio-One; Frickenhausen, Germany)
169 and 29 μL of 1 mol L⁻¹ Folin–Ciocalteu reagent were added. After 3 min incubation in
170 darkness, 192 μL of 0.4 % Na₂CO₃ 2 % NaOH were added. The absorbance was measured
171 at 750 nm using a microplate reader (Tecan Infinite M200, Männedorf, Switzerland) after
172 1 h incubation in darkness. The TPC was expressed as g chlorogenic acid equivalents
173 (CAE) kg⁻¹ dry weight (dw). Each sample was analysed in triplicate.

174 **2.5. Total antioxidant capacity**

175 Total antioxidant capacity was directly related to the ability to scavenge the 2,2-diphenyl-
176 1-picrilhidrazilo free radical. DPPH assay was performed following the method described
177 by Martínez-Zamora et al. (2021). For that, 194 μL of DPPH (0.7 mM) solution were added
178 to 21 μL of sprout extract. The mixture was incubated for 30 min in darkness. The TAC by

179 DPPH was measured by changes in absorbance at 515 nm. Obtained data were expressed
180 as g of Trolox equivalents (TE) kg⁻¹ dw. Each sample was analysed in triplicate.

181 **2.6. Extraction and analysis of Glucosinolates**

182 Extraction and analysis of GLs content was carried out following the method described by
183 Moreira-Rodríguez et al. (2017b). Briefly, 10 mL of ethanol/water (70:30, v/v) previously
184 heated at 70 °C in a bath were added to sprouts powder (0.2 ± 0.01 g) followed by the
185 addition of 50 µL of 3 mM sinigrin as internal standard. To ensure myrosinase inactivation,
186 samples were incubated at 70 °C for 30 min and vortexed at 0, 10, and 20 min. The extracts
187 were removed from the water bath, rapidly cooled on an ice bath, and centrifuged at 18,000
188 g for 10 min at 4 °C (L-90K Ultracentrifuge Beckman Coulter, rotor type 45 70Ti). The
189 clarified extract (supernatant) was recovered for GLs analysis. Immediately after the
190 extraction, GLs were desulphated and purified using disposable polypropylene columns
191 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). Columns were prepared by adding 0.5
192 mL of MilliQ water, followed by 0.5 mL of Sephadex A-25 and 0.5 mL of MilliQ water.
193 Then, 3 mL of clarified ethanolic extract were added into a prepared column and allowed
194 to drip through slowly. Columns were washed with 2 × 0.5 mL of MilliQ water followed
195 by 2 × 0.5 mL of 0.02 M sodium acetate. Purified sulfatase (75 µL) was added to each
196 sample and left at room temperature overnight (16 h). Desulfoglucosinolates were eluted
197 with a total of 1.25 mL of water and kept at -80 °C until UHPLC analysis. Analysis and
198 identification of GLs were conducted according to Moreira-Rodríguez et al. (2017b). For
199 that, an Ultra High Performance Liquid Chromatography (UHPLC) instrument (Shimadzu,
200 Kyoto, Japan) equipped with a DGU-20A degasser, LC-30AD quaternary pump, SIL-
201 30AC autosampler, CTO-10AS column heater, and SPDM-20A photodiode array detector
202 was used. Chromatographic analyses were carried out into a Gemini C18 column (250 mm
203 x 4.6 mm, 5 µm particle size; Phenomenex, Torrance CA, USA). Separation of

204 desulfoglucosinolates in the UHPLC system was achieved using water (phase A) and
205 acetonitrile (phase B) as mobile phases with a flow rate of 1.5 mL min⁻¹ and a gradient of
206 0/100, 28/80, 30/100 (min/% phase A) with an injection volume of 20 µL.
207 Desulfoglucosinolates were detected at 227 nm and identified compounds are shown in
208 Figure 2. The results were expressed as g kg⁻¹ dw. Each sample was extracted and analysed
209 in triplicate.
210

211

212 **Figure 2.** UHPLC chromatograms (shown at 227 nm) of identified glucosinolates from ethanol/water (70:30, v/v) extracts of broccoli and radish
 213 seeds and sprouts treated with UV (CTRL, UVB, UVC, and UVC+B) during 10 d stored at 4 °C. Identified peaks are in broccoli sprouts (A) are:
 214 (1) Glucoiberin, (2) Progoitrin, (3) Glucoraphanin, (4) 4-hydroxy-glucobrassicin, (5) Glucoerucin, (6) Glucobrassicin, (7) 4-methoxy-
 215 glucobrassicin, and (8) Neoglucobrassicin. Identified peaks are in radish sprouts (B) are: (1) Glucoiberin, (2) Progoitrin, (3) Glucoraphenin, (4) 4-
 216 hydroxy-glucobrassicin, (5) Dehydroerucin, (6) Glucobrassicin, (7) 4-methoxy-glucobrassicin, and (8) Neoglucobrassicin.

217 **2.7. Extraction and analysis of isothiocyanates**

218 Sulforaphane content was analysed according to Martínez-Hernández et al. (2019). For that,
219 0.25 g of freeze-dried sprouts were mixed with 5 mL of milliQ water (pH=6) and incubated
220 at 45 °C for 2 h to allow glucoraphanin conversion to sulforaphane. Then, 25 mL MTBE
221 were added and sonicated for 1 min. This mixture was dewatered using 5.5 g of sodium
222 sulphate and filtered through Whatman 41 filter papers. The collected extract was passed
223 through an activated (3 mL MTBE + 3 mL ethyl acetate + 3 mL air) SI-1 silica cartridge
224 (Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA) being discarded the eluent. After that, sulforaphane
225 was eluted with 2 mL of methanol and evaporated in a rotary evaporator at 45 °C. The final
226 dry residue was resuspended in 1 mL acetonitrile and filtered (0.45 µm).

227 Sulforaphane extracts were analysis in an UHPLC (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with
228 a DGU-20A degasser, LC-30AD quaternary pump, SIL-30AC autosampler, CTO-10AS
229 column heater, and SPDM-20A photodiode array detector was used. Chromatographic
230 analyses were carried out into a Gemini C18 column (250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5 µm particle
231 size; Phenomenex, Torrance CA, USA). For that, the mobile phases used were 20 mmol L⁻¹
232 ammonium formate (phase A) and acetonitrile (phase B). The injection volume was 5 µL
233 (draw speed of 50 µL min⁻¹), flow rate 0.6 mL min⁻¹, temperature at 25 °C and detection
234 wavelength at 196 nm. Sulforaphane was quantified using DL-sulforaphane standard
235 (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) and results were expressed as g kg⁻¹ dw. Each sample
236 was analysed in triplicate.

237 **2.8. Statistical analyses**

238 The experiment was a two-factor (treatment × time) design subjected to analysis of variance
239 (ANOVA) using Statgraphics Plus software (v. 5.1. Statpoint Technologies. Inc.
240 Warrenton. VA. USA). Statistical significance was assessed at the level $p < 0.05$, and
241 Tukey's multiple range test was used to separate means.

242 3. RESULTS

243 3.1. Characterization

244 The morphological characteristics of 10-d broccoli (*Brassica olearacea* var. *italica*) and
245 radish (*Raphanus sativus*) sprouts are shown in Table 1. The broccoli sprout length
246 (cotyledon + hypocotyl + radical) was 6.21 ± 0.67 cm, while the radish sprout length was
247 6.71 ± 0.67 cm. Radish sprouts presented a higher thickness of the hypocotyl and they
248 were yellowish in colour, while broccoli sprouts presented smaller and greener leaves.
249 Furthermore, fresh weight/dry weight (FW/DW) ratio was lower in radish sprouts, which
250 means that dry mass of broccoli sprouts was lower.

251 After harvesting broccoli sprouts, the mesophilic microbial load was 8.69 ± 0.01 cfu g⁻¹
252 fw, while psychrophilic count was 8.17 ± 0.02 cfu g⁻¹ fw. Besides, broccoli sprouts had
253 5.62 ± 0.13 cfu enterobacteria g⁻¹ fw and 6.30 ± 0.00 cfu moulds and yeast g⁻¹ fw.

254 In a similar way, on the processing day, the mesophilic load of radish sprouts was $8.62 \pm$
255 0.05 cfu g⁻¹ fw, whereas the psychrophilic count was 8.33 ± 0.07 cfu g⁻¹ fw. As well,
256 radish sprouts had 5.62 ± 0.13 cfu enterobacteria g⁻¹ fw and 5.11 ± 0.12 cfu moulds and
257 yeast g⁻¹ fw, which was also maintained throughout the refrigerated period with no
258 significant differences.

259 3.2. Total phenolic content

260 The germination process of radish seeds during 10 d at 20 °C naturally increased the TPC
261 by 108 % in CTRL sprouts while its content was higher increased in UVC, UVB, and
262 UVC+B treated samples by 125, 160, and 187 %, respectively (Figure 3).

263

264

265 **Figure 3.** Total phenolic content of UV treated broccoli (A) and radish (B) sprouts stored for 10 d at 4 °C. T: treatment; t: time. n.s.: no
 266 significant differences. ***: P < 0.001. *: significant differences regarding CTRL samples.

267

268 The evolution of TPC during storage at 4 °C was similar in all treatments. During the first
269 4 d of storage, the TPC were maintained at similar values, however, an increase in TPC
270 was observed after the 7th d of storage. Particularly, after the first UV application on day
271 0, UVB and UVC+B treatments significantly increased the TPC by 25 and 38 %, respectively,
272 compared to the CTRL. This fact was also observed in UVC+B treated
273 radish sprouts when the second UV application was performed after 1 d at 4°C. The UVC
274 and UVC+B treatments increased the TPC after 4 d at 4 °C compared to CTRL and again
275 UVC+B also reported an increase after the shelf-life period of after 10 d at 4 °C regarding
276 CTRL.

277 In contrast, the TPC of broccoli sprouts increased during germination at 20 °C. Indeed,
278 the TPC was increased by 255, 306, 298, and 295 % in CTRL, UVC, UVB, and UVC+B
279 treatments compared to broccoli seed, respectively. In this case, UVC showed the highest
280 values of TPC on day 0 and 1 after harvesting, while UVB showed highest TPC on day
281 10 at 4 °C. Although no differences were observed after UV treatments, a clear tendency
282 to enhance the TPC have been also found in broccoli sprouts on days 0, 1, and 10 of the
283 refrigerated storage.

284 **3.3. Total antioxidant capacity**

285 From a general point of view, the TAC of the studied sprouts increased during the
286 germination, but when they reach the optimal vegetative growth as a ready to eat sprout,
287 their TAC was maintained during the postharvest storage at 4 °C (Figure 4).

288

289

290 **Figure 4.** Total antioxidant capacity measured by DPPH of UV treated broccoli (A) and radish (B) sprouts stored for 10 d at 4 °C. T: treatment; t:
 291 time. ***: P < 0.001. *: significant differences regarding CTRL samples.

292

293 The initial TAC of 10-d CTRL radish sprouts was 7.5 g TE kg⁻¹ dw, which was increased
294 after the first UV application by 28, 55 and 72 % in UVC, UVB and UVC+B treatments,
295 respectively. Although UVC stood out after both UV applications, its effect was not
296 maintained throughout the 10 d at 4 °C. Indeed, UVB was higher throughout the
297 postharvest period, while UVC+B stood out on day 4. As it happened with the TPC
298 (Figure 3), the TAC increased after 7 d at 4 °C in all treatments.

299 The germination process during 10 d at 20 °C increased by 208 % the initial TAC in
300 broccoli seeds (6.0 g TE kg⁻¹ dw). In this case, the effect of the UV treatments was not
301 observed after the two UV applications. The TAC of UV-untreated broccoli sprouts was
302 maintained in the same range throughout the storage period at 4 °C. However, on day 7,
303 the TAC increased by 40 % in UVB and UVC+B treatments compared to CTRL, while,
304 on day 10, an increase of 28 % was found in all UV treatments regarding CTRL.

305 **3.4. Glucosinolate content**

306 According to UHPLC chromatograms, the identified aliphatic GLs derived from alanine,
307 leucine, isoleucine, methionine or valine were (1) Glucoiberin, (2) Progoitrin, (3)
308 Glucoraphanin / Glucoraphenin, and (5) Glucoerucin / Dehydroerucin, for broccoli /
309 radish sprouts, respectively. Meanwhile, indoyl GLs derived from tryptophan found were
310 (4) 4-Hydroxy-glucobrassicin, (6) Glucobrassicin, (7) 4-Methoxy-glucobrassicin, and (8)
311 Neoglucobrassicin (Figure 2).

312 The amount of these eight GLs for broccoli and radish sprouts is shown in Table 2 and
313 Table 3, respectively. The total GL content of both *Brassicaceae* sprouts is presented in
314 Figure 5.

315 **Table 2.** Glucosinolate content (g kg⁻¹ dw) of UV treated broccoli sprouts during a shelf-life period of 10 d at 4 °C.

<i>Treatment</i>	<i>Day of analysis</i>	<i>Glucoiberin-dsg</i>	<i>Progoitrin-dsg</i>	<i>Glucoraphanin-dsg</i>	<i>4-hydroxy-glucobrassicin-dsg</i>	<i>Glucoerucin-dsg</i>	<i>Glucobrassicin-dsg</i>	<i>4-methoxy-glucobrassicin-dsg</i>	<i>Neoglucobrassicin-dsg</i>
	Seed	6.56 ± 0.99 ^{a/a/a/a}	0.12 ± 0.05 ^{b/b/b/b}	16.39 ± 1.27 ^{a/a/a/a}	17.17 ± 1.22 ^{a/a/a/a}	8.69 ± 0.78 ^{a/a/a/a}	0.27 ± 0.05 ^{b/c/d/b}	0.36 ± 0.04 ^{c/c/c/d}	0.58 ± 0.07 ^{e/c/d/e}
CTRL	0	2.75 ± 0.23 ^b	0.79 ± 0.17 ^a	6.92 ± 1.08 ^b	6.82 ± 1.04 ^b	5.42 ± 0.06 ^b	2.37 ± 0.45 ^a	9.19 ± 0.61 ^{Bab}	6.07 ± 0.39 ^{Dbc}
	1	2.56 ± 0.32 ^b	0.79 ± 0.17 ^a	6.26 ± 0.18 ^{Cb}	4.10 ± 0.63 ^c	4.71 ± 0.46 ^{Cbc}	2.36 ± 0.31 ^a	7.81 ± 0.02 ^{Cb}	6.59 ± 0.79 ^{Ab}
	4	2.75 ± 0.18 ^{ABb}	0.72 ± 0.03 ^a	6.59 ± 0.64 ^{ABb}	3.02 ± 0.23 ^{Cc}	4.29 ± 0.19 ^{Bbc}	1.89 ± 0.31 ^{Ba}	8.97 ± 0.28 ^{Bab}	4.37 ± 0.07 ^{Dd}
	7	2.73 ± 0.26 ^{Bb}	0.86 ± 0.05 ^a	7.09 ± 1.06 ^b	4.22 ± 0.61 ^{Bc}	3.98 ± 0.62 ^{Bc}	2.16 ± 0.27 ^{Ca}	10.52 ± 0.76 ^{Ba}	4.93 ± 0.54 ^{Ccd}
	10	2.61 ± 0.09 ^{ABb}	0.86 ± 0.07 ^a	5.61 ± 0.33 ^{ABb}	4.09 ± 0.22 ^c	4.07 ± 0.56 ^{bc}	2.26 ± 0.04 ^{Ba}	10.39 ± 1.22 ^{Ca}	7.89 ± 0.28 ^{Ca}
UVC	0	2.58 ± 0.17 ^b	0.79 ± 0.18 ^a	6.81 ± 1.05 ^b	6.27 ± 0.73 ^b	4.98 ± 0.54 ^b	2.22 ± 0.10 ^b	7.27 ± 0.50 ^{Cb}	7.84 ± 0.65 ^{Ca}
	1	3.23 ± 0.16 ^b	0.83 ± 0.19 ^a	7.97 ± 0.34 ^{Bb}	4.89 ± 1.09 ^{bc}	5.68 ± 0.41 ^{Bb}	2.26 ± 0.50 ^b	8.02 ± 0.04 ^{Cb}	6.05 ± 0.72 ^{ABb}
	4	2.67 ± 0.21 ^{ABb}	0.82 ± 0.12 ^a	6.80 ± 0.38 ^{ABb}	3.49 ± 0.06 ^{BCc}	5.05 ± 0.58 ^{ABb}	2.50 ± 0.28 ^{ABab}	8.03 ± 0.89 ^{Bb}	5.52 ± 0.06 ^{Cb}
	7	3.40 ± 0.12 ^{Ab}	0.87 ± 0.06 ^a	8.02 ± 0.25 ^b	5.64 ± 0.67 ^{ABbc}	5.90 ± 0.12 ^{Ab}	3.09 ± 0.03 ^{Ba}	11.44 ± 0.40 ^{Ba}	7.88 ± 0.17 ^{Ba}
	10	3.09 ± 0.36 ^{Ab}	1.01 ± 0.12 ^a	7.64 ± 1.31 ^{Ab}	4.53 ± 0.43 ^{bc}	5.19 ± 0.55 ^b	2.70 ± 0.10 ^{Aab}	12.24 ± 0.18 ^{Ba}	7.68 ± 0.23 ^{Ca}
UVB	0	2.64 ± 0.10 ^b	0.83 ± 0.17 ^a	6.42 ± 0.48 ^c	7.61 ± 1.48 ^b	5.11 ± 0.43 ^{cd}	2.51 ± 0.22 ^{bc}	11.34 ± 0.39 ^{Ab}	11.21 ± 0.06 ^{Aab}
	1	3.28 ± 0.47 ^b	0.69 ± 0.14 ^a	9.49 ± 0.20 ^{Ab}	4.68 ± 1.27 ^c	6.86 ± 0.14 ^{Ab}	2.11 ± 0.24 ^c	10.22 ± 0.22 ^{Ab}	6.29 ± 0.83 ^{ABc}
	4	3.20 ± 0.18 ^{Ab}	0.86 ± 0.08 ^a	7.65 ± 0.43 ^{Abc}	4.85 ± 0.11 ^{Abc}	5.93 ± 0.27 ^{Abc}	2.73 ± 0.30 ^{Ab}	11.14 ± 0.07 ^{Ab}	10.13 ± 0.82 ^{Ab}
	7	3.35 ± 0.27 ^{Ab}	0.95 ± 0.08 ^a	7.40 ± 0.41 ^c	6.39 ± 1.09 ^{Abc}	5.74 ± 0.05 ^{Abcd}	3.62 ± 0.01 ^{Aa}	15.11 ± 1.14 ^{Aa}	10.04 ± 1.19 ^{Ab}
	10	2.74 ± 0.43 ^{ABb}	0.97 ± 0.13 ^a	6.52 ± 0.79 ^{ABc}	4.18 ± 0.23 ^c	4.63 ± 0.41 ^d	3.02 ± 0.25 ^{Ab}	15.63 ± 0.08 ^{Aa}	12.28 ± 0.06 ^{Aa}
UVC+B	0	2.86 ± 0.54 ^{bc}	0.75 ± 0.15 ^a	6.91 ± 1.57 ^{bc}	4.85 ± 1.34 ^b	5.05 ± 0.32 ^b	2.02 ± 0.48 ^a	7.07 ± 0.09 ^{Cc}	9.81 ± 0.18 ^{Ba}
	1	2.50 ± 0.07 ^{bc}	0.72 ± 0.03 ^a	5.74 ± 0.26 ^{Cbc}	2.84 ± 0.49 ^b	4.02 ± 0.33 ^{Cb}	1.62 ± 0.25 ^a	8.78 ± 0.15 ^{Bb}	4.76 ± 0.08 ^{Bd}
	4	2.65 ± 0.24 ^{Bbc}	0.80 ± 0.02 ^a	5.95 ± 0.52 ^{Bbc}	4.62 ± 0.86 ^{ABb}	4.90 ± 0.50 ^{ABb}	2.00 ± 0.29 ^{ABa}	8.55 ± 0.12 ^{Bb}	6.71 ± 0.10 ^{Bc}
	7	3.38 ± 0.12 ^{Ab}	0.96 ± 0.10 ^a	7.82 ± 1.11 ^b	4.18 ± 0.58 ^{Bb}	5.30 ± 0.66 ^{Ab}	1.53 ± 0.02 ^{Da}	9.85 ± 0.10 ^{Ba}	5.89 ± 0.89 ^{BCc}
	10	1.99 ± 0.20 ^{Bc}	0.98 ± 0.17 ^a	4.93 ± 0.48 ^{Bc}	3.61 ± 0.78 ^b	4.00 ± 0.29 ^b	1.49 ± 0.01 ^{Ca}	6.99 ± 0.13 ^{Dc}	8.77 ± 0.07 ^{Bb}

316 Different capital letters denote significant differences (p<0.05) among different treatments for the same sampling time. Different lowercase letters denote significant differences

317 (p<0.05) among different sampling times for the same treatment. Absence of letters indicates that there are no significant differences (p<0.05).

319 **Table 3.** Glucosinolate content (g kg⁻¹ dw) of UV treated radish sprouts during a shelf-life period of 10 d at 4 °C.

<i>Treatment</i>	<i>Day of analysis</i>	<i>Glucoiberin-dsg</i>	<i>Progoitrin-dsg</i>	<i>Glucoraphenin-dsg</i>	<i>4-hydroxy-glucobrassicin-dsg</i>	<i>Dehydroerucin-dsg</i>	<i>Glucobrassicin-dsg</i>	<i>4-methoxy-glucobrassicin-dsg</i>	<i>Neoglucobrassicin-dsg</i>
	Seed	0.28 ± 0.01 ab/c/c/b	0.65 ± 0.02 ^{b/b/c/c}	197.6 ± 9.9 ^{a/a/a/a}	26.4 ± 4.4 ^{a/a/a/a}	12 ± 1 ^{c/c/c/b}	0.39 ± 0.04 ^{d/c/b/b}	3.0 ± 0.0 ^{d/d/d/c}	50.55 ± 4.97 ^{a/a/a/a}
CTRL	0	0.24 ± 0.01 ^{Bb}	0.71 ± 0.13 ^{ab}	46.7 ± 0.8 ^{Bb}	14.3 ± 4.1 ^b	96 ± 6 ^{Cb}	1.01 ± 0.09 ^{ab}	7.9 ± 0.5 ^{Bc}	0.36 ± 0.06 ^{Bc}
	1	0.40 ± 0.03 ^{Ba}	0.69 ± 0.03 ^{Bb}	40.5 ± 8.9 ^b	13.1 ± 1.5 ^{ABb}	102 ± 5 ^{Cab}	0.72 ± 0.01 ^{Bc}	9.7 ± 0.2 ^{Bc}	4.18 ± 0.87 ^{bc}
	4	0.39 ± 0.06 ^{Ba}	1.05 ± 0.07 ^a	46.8 ± 6.4 ^{Cb}	14.5 ± 1.6 ^b	111 ± 6 ^{Ba}	0.96 ± 0.01 ^{ab}	14.5 ± 0.5 ^b	6.11 ± 0.38 ^b
	7	0.37 ± 0.08 ^a	0.94 ± 0.11 ^{ab}	52.5 ± 3.7 ^b	13.6 ± 2.4 ^b	109 ± 2 ^{Ba}	1.20 ± 0.01 ^a	15.4 ± 0.2 ^{Cab}	1.37 ± 0.19 ^{Bbc}
	10	0.39 ± 0.03 ^{Ba}	0.89 ± 0.24 ^{ab}	52.1 ± 0.1 ^{Bb}	14.6 ± 0.0 ^b	109 ± 1 ^{Ba}	1.20 ± 0.31 ^a	16.9 ± 1.5 ^{Ca}	1.25 ± 0.21 ^{bc}
UVC	0	0.33 ± 0.04 ^{ABc}	0.72 ± 0.13 ^b	77.8 ± 15.3 ^{Ab}	17.2 ± 2.8 ^b	142 ± 8 ^{ABa}	0.84 ± 0.09 ^{abc}	9.0 ± 2.2 ^{ABc}	1.13 ± 0.18 ^{Bb}
	1	0.38 ± 0.01 ^{Bbc}	1.09 ± 0.14 ^{Aa}	49.1 ± 12.9 ^c	13.1 ± 2.3 ^{ABb}	129 ± 8 ^{Bab}	0.77 ± 0.02 ^{ABbc}	8.3 ± 1.2 ^{Bc}	4.69 ± 1.09 ^b
	4	0.50 ± 0.03 ^{ABa}	1.27 ± 0.09 ^a	87.4 ± 6.2 ^{Ab}	16.9 ± 0.8 ^b	114 ± 4 ^{Bb}	1.31 ± 0.36 ^a	15.6 ± 1.0 ^b	6.56 ± 0.64 ^b
	7	0.45 ± 0.00 ^{ab}	1.07 ± 0.12 ^a	69.8 ± 6.8 ^{bc}	15.7 ± 1.3 ^b	124 ± 8 ^{Bab}	1.19 ± 0.18 ^{ab}	17.4 ± 0.5 ^{Bb}	3.51 ± 0.72 ^{Ab}
	10	0.47 ± 0.07 ^{ABab}	1.05 ± 0.06 ^a	65.0 ± 4.6 ^{Bbc}	16.1 ± 2.0 ^b	133 ± 10 ^{ABab}	1.06 ± 0.10 ^{ab}	20.8 ± 0.9 ^{Ba}	1.57 ± 0.75 ^b
UVB	0	0.37 ± 0.05 ^{Abc}	0.82 ± 0.13 ^{bc}	64.5 ± 6.7 ^{ABbc}	17.2 ± 1.2 ^b	170 ± 19 ^{Aa}	0.73 ± 0.26 ^b	8.8 ± 1.5 ^{Bc}	3.95 ± 0.32 ^{Ab}
	1	0.53 ± 0.12 ^{ABab}	1.01 ± 0.07 ^{Aab}	60.7 ± 8.6 ^c	12.1 ± 2.5 ^{Bb}	159 ± 6 ^{Aab}	0.69 ± 0.12 ^{Bb}	9.8 ± 0.3 ^{Bc}	3.76 ± 0.61 ^b
	4	0.60 ± 0.10 ^{Aa}	1.35 ± 0.20 ^a	86.7 ± 12.3 ^{Ab}	15.4 ± 1.5 ^b	152 ± 10 ^{Aab}	1.15 ± 0.14 ^a	18.2 ± 1.6 ^b	6.62 ± 1.07 ^b
	7	0.45 ± 0.01 ^{abc}	1.02 ± 0.20 ^{ab}	64.4 ± 9.1 ^{bc}	12.3 ± 0.4 ^b	168 ± 0 ^{Aa}	1.20 ± 0.01 ^a	25.3 ± 0.0 ^{Aa}	0.99 ± 0.04 ^{Bb}
	10	0.58 ± 0.10 ^{Aab}	1.20 ± 0.06 ^a	86.7 ± 5.4 ^{Ab}	16.4 ± 2.9 ^b	136 ± 16 ^{Ab}	1.24 ± 0.11 ^a	27.5 ± 1.2 ^{Aa}	1.51 ± 0.12 ^b
UVC+B	0	0.41 ± 0.05 ^{Ab}	0.75 ± 0.06 ^{bc}	65.9 ± 4.6 ^{ABb}	16.3 ± 1.4 ^b	139 ± 3 ^{Ba}	0.81 ± 0.28 ^{ab}	12.8 ± 1.2 ^{Ab}	3.86 ± 0.92 ^{Ab}
	1	0.65 ± 0.11 ^{Aa}	1.02 ± 0.12 ^{Aab}	58.7 ± 2.1 ^b	18.2 ± 2.7 ^{Ab}	132 ± 9 ^{Ba}	1.10 ± 0.23 ^{Aa}	12.4 ± 1.3 ^{Ab}	4.31 ± 0.33 ^b
	4	0.45 ± 0.10 ^{ABb}	1.13 ± 0.07 ^a	67.3 ± 1.1 ^{Bb}	17.4 ± 1.8 ^b	126 ± 19 ^{ABa}	1.15 ± 0.29 ^a	15.8 ± 3.0 ^b	6.77 ± 0.42 ^b
	7	0.45 ± 0.06 ^b	0.93 ± 0.09 ^{abc}	57.4 ± 2.3 ^b	16.8 ± 3.0 ^b	120 ± 9 ^{Ba}	1.04 ± 0.22 ^a	15.6 ± 1.2 ^b	2.42 ± 0.16 ^{ABb}
	10	0.48 ± 0.07 ^{ABab}	1.02 ± 0.18 ^{ab}	59.0 ± 8.6 ^{Bb}	11.5 ± 1.6 ^b	116 ± 1 ^{ABa}	0.94 ± 0.14 ^{ab}	23.2 ± 2.1 ^{Ba}	1.02 ± 0.09 ^b

320 Different capital letters denote significant differences (p<0.05) among different treatments for the same sampling time. Different lowercase letters denote significant differences

321 (p<0.05) among different sampling times for the same treatment. Absence of letters indicates that there are no significant differences (p<0.05).

322

323 **Figure 5.** Total glucosinolates of UV treated broccoli (A) and radish (B) sprouts stored for 10 d at 4 °C. T: treatment; t: time. ***: P < 0.001. *:
 324 significant differences regarding CTRL samples.

325

326 Aliphatic GLs accounted the 72 % of the total in the radish seed, increasing up to 85 %
327 in the radish sprouts. The predominant GL found was Dehydroerucin-dsg (also known as
328 Glucoraphasatin), reporting 57 % of total, but only a 4 % in the seed. As appreciated in
329 Table 3, the radish seeds were rich in Glucoraphenin-dsg, with a 68 % of total. In fact,
330 Glucoraphenin-dsg was the second most common GL in radish sprouts, representing a 27
331 % of total.

332 The initial total GL content was $291 \text{ g kg}^{-1} \text{ dw}$ in the radish seed, which decreased by 58
333 % after 10 d of sprouting at 20 °C (CTRL). The UV application stimulated the total GL
334 content while preserving the content initially present in the seed. After the first UV dose,
335 an increase of 33, 37 and 30 % was observed in UVC, UVB and UVC+B, respectively,
336 compared to CTRL. After that, the second UV application increased by 31 and 25 % the
337 total GL content in the UVB and UVC+B radish sprouts, respectively. The residual effect
338 of the UV application was positively maintained during 10 d at 4 °C. UVB treatment
339 presented the highest concentration of total GLs during the shelf-life period. UVC+B
340 treatment did not have a better effect, and no differences were observed with the other
341 UV treated sprouts. In fact, on days 7 and 10 the combination of both UV lightings
342 considerably reduced the total GL content without differences compared to CTRL radish
343 sprouts.

344 In the case of broccoli seed, the aliphatic GLs were also the major group found,
345 accounting for 63 % of the total content. However, this GL group was reduced by
346 germination representing only the 39 % after 10 sprouting days. At this moment, the
347 predominant GL was 4-Methoxy-glucobrassicin-dsg in broccoli sprouts, followed by
348 Neoglucobrassicin-dsg and Glucoraphenin-dsg. Broccoli seeds were rich in 4-Hydroxy-
349 glucobrassicin-dsg and Glucoraphenin-dsg, with a 33 and 34 % of the total content,
350 respectively (Table 2).

351 The initial concentration of total GLs in broccoli seed was 50.1 g kg⁻¹ dw, which followed
352 the same tendency previously described for radish sprouts. The application of UVB had
353 an amelioration effect on the biosynthesis of GLs and these levels were maintained like
354 those reported for seeds. On the minimal processing day, the total GL content was 40.3 g
355 kg⁻¹ dw in CTRL broccoli sprouts. After this moment, when light stressors were applied,
356 UVB reported an increase of 18 % after the first UV application, reaching an increase of
357 44 % on the 7th d. The UVC and UVC+B treatments did not positively affect to the GLs
358 content. In fact, the UVC+B treatment reported similar amounts to CTRL sprouts.

359 Radish sprouts presented 5-fold more GLs content than broccoli sprouts (Figure 5). The
360 total GL content was markedly reduced after the sprouting period and then maintained
361 throughout the shelf-life period in CTRL sprouts. UVB lighting was able to induce de
362 biosynthesis of GLs to a similar amount to that found in seeds and maintained it
363 throughout the postharvest period.

364 **3.5. Isothiocyanate content**

365 According to results found in broccoli sprouts, CTRL samples reported 0.05 g kg⁻¹ dw of
366 sulforaphane at harvest, accounting the 8 % of the total sulforaphane content (Table 4).
367 After the first UV application, no differences were observed among treatments. However,
368 the second UVB and UVC+B application increased by 37.5 % the biologically active
369 sulforaphane content regarding CTRL samples, which can be due to the increase in the
370 glucoraphanin content of UVB-treated sprouts by 51 %. This increase was not observed
371 in UVC+B treatment. The residual effect of the UVB treatment on sulforaphane was not
372 observed from day 4, this is corroborated by the fact that the glucoraphanin compound
373 remained constant in those days. In the case of UV-untreated 10-d broccoli sprouts, only
374 the 0.8 % of the glucoraphanin compound was converted into sulforaphane.

375 **Table 4.** Sulforaphane content (g kg⁻¹ dw) of UV treated broccoli and radish sprouts during a shelf-life period of 10 d at 4 °C.

<i>Treatment</i>	Day of analysis	Broccoli			Radish		
		Sulforaphane nitrile	Sulforaphane	Total Sulforaphane	Sulforaphene nitrile	Sulforaphene	Total Sulforaphene
	Seed	0.53 ± 0.10 ^{bc/c/b/bc}	0.06 ± 0.01 ^{ab/a/b/b}	0.59 ± 0.11 ^{b/c/e/bc}	0.71 ± 0.25 ^{c/c/c/d}	0.10 ± 0.03 ^{b/b/c/b}	0.81 ± 0.28 ^{b/b/c/c}
CTRL	0	0.55 ± 0.16 ^{Bbc}	0.05 ± 0.01 ^{ABbc}	0.60 ± 0.17 ^{Bb}	0.85 ± 0.21 ^{Bbc}	2.65 ± 0.43 ^{Ba}	3.49 ± 0.61 ^{Ca}
	1	0.46 ± 0.11 ^{Bc}	0.08 ± 0.01 ^{Ba}	0.54 ± 0.10 ^{Bb}	0.86 ± 0.21 ^{Bbc}	2.87 ± 0.23 ^{Ba}	3.73 ± 0.41 ^{Ba}
	4	0.80 ± 0.09 ^{Bab}	0.03 ± 0.00 ^{cd}	0.83 ± 0.09 ^{Bab}	1.62 ± 0.27 ^{ABa}	2.78 ± 0.29 ^{Ba}	4.41 ± 0.25 ^{Ca}
	7	0.89 ± 0.09 ^{ABa}	0.04 ± 0.01 ^{cd}	0.92 ± 0.09 ^{ABa}	1.30 ± 0.19 ^{Bab}	2.51 ± 0.09 ^{Ba}	3.81 ± 0.28 ^{Ca}
	10	0.98 ± 0.05 ^{ABa}	0.02 ± 0.01 ^{ABd}	1.00 ± 0.05 ^{ABa}	1.60 ± 0.03 ^{Ba}	2.70 ± 0.19 ^{Ba}	4.30 ± 0.18 ^{Ba}
UVC	0	1.06 ± 0.05 ^{Aa}	0.03 ± 0.01 ^{Bb}	1.09 ± 0.05 ^{Aab}	1.67 ± 0.05 ^{Aa}	4.17 ± 0.46 ^{Aa}	5.84 ± 0.51 ^{ABa}
	1	0.84 ± 0.02 ^{Ab}	0.07 ± 0.01 ^{Ba}	0.91 ± 0.02 ^{Ab}	1.17 ± 0.16 ^{ABb}	3.53 ± 0.49 ^{ABa}	4.70 ± 0.66 ^{ABa}
	4	1.12 ± 0.07 ^{Aa}	0.03 ± 0.01 ^b	1.15 ± 0.07 ^{Aa}	1.57 ± 0.04 ^{Bab}	3.64 ± 0.28 ^{ABa}	5.21 ± 0.30 ^{BCa}
	7	1.06 ± 0.02 ^{Aa}	0.03 ± 0.02 ^b	1.10 ± 0.01 ^{Aa}	1.60 ± 0.17 ^{ABa}	3.26 ± 0.36 ^{ABa}	4.86 ± 0.49 ^{BCa}
	10	1.07 ± 0.08 ^{Aa}	0.03 ± 0.00 ^{Ab}	1.10 ± 0.09 ^{Aa}	1.89 ± 0.10 ^{ABa}	3.48 ± 0.34 ^{ABa}	5.37 ± 0.35 ^{Aa}
UVB	0	0.96 ± 0.09 ^{Aa}	0.07 ± 0.02 ^{Ab}	1.03 ± 0.10 ^{Aab}	1.97 ± 0.05 ^{Aa}	4.56 ± 0.21 ^{Aa}	6.53 ± 0.15 ^{Aa}
	1	0.71 ± 0.03 ^{Ab}	0.11 ± 0.00 ^{Aa}	0.83 ± 0.03 ^{Ab}	1.45 ± 0.18 ^{Ab}	3.55 ± 0.44 ^{ABb}	5.00 ± 0.55 ^{ABb}
	4	0.92 ± 0.11 ^{ABa}	0.04 ± 0.01 ^{bc}	0.96 ± 0.10 ^{ABab}	2.03 ± 0.22 ^{ABa}	3.96 ± 0.41 ^{Aab}	5.99 ± 0.46 ^{ABab}
	7	0.97 ± 0.04 ^{Aa}	0.01 ± 0.01 ^{cd}	0.98 ± 0.03 ^{Aab}	1.86 ± 0.18 ^{Aab}	3.45 ± 0.44 ^{Ab}	5.30 ± 0.59 ^{ABb}
	10	1.04 ± 0.04 ^{Aa}	0.01 ± 0.00 ^{Bd}	1.05 ± 0.04 ^{Aa}	1.84 ± 0.10 ^{ABab}	3.36 ± 0.29 ^{ABb}	5.21 ± 0.22 ^{Ab}
UVC+B	0	0.30 ± 0.12 ^{Bc}	0.08 ± 0.01 ^{Aab}	0.38 ± 0.11 ^{Bc}	1.11 ± 0.25 ^{Bcd}	3.39 ± 0.71 ^{ABa}	4.50 ± 0.95 ^{BCb}
	1	0.75 ± 0.12 ^{Aab}	0.11 ± 0.01 ^{Aa}	0.86 ± 0.11 ^{Aab}	1.44 ± 0.27 ^{Abc}	3.96 ± 0.41 ^{Aa}	5.39 ± 0.65 ^{Aab}
	4	0.94 ± 0.06 ^{ABa}	0.03 ± 0.01 ^c	0.97 ± 0.05 ^{ABa}	2.12 ± 0.18 ^{Aa}	4.42 ± 0.55 ^{Aa}	6.54 ± 0.61 ^{Aa}
	7	0.76 ± 0.10 ^{Bab}	0.02 ± 0.01 ^c	0.78 ± 0.11 ^{Bab}	1.92 ± 0.11 ^{Aab}	4.06 ± 0.31 ^{Aa}	5.99 ± 0.07 ^{Aab}
	10	0.82 ± 0.06 ^{Ba}	0.02 ± 0.01 ^{ABc}	0.84 ± 0.07 ^{Bab}	2.07 ± 0.19 ^{Aab}	3.83 ± 0.51 ^{Aa}	5.89 ± 0.34 ^{Aab}

376 Different capital letters denote significant differences (p<0.05) among different treatments for the same sampling time. Different lowercase letters denote significant differences
377 (p<0.05) among different sampling times for the same treatment. Absence of letters indicates that there are no significant differences (p<0.05).

379 Concerning radish sprouts, around 70 % of the total sulforaphane content corresponded
380 to the sulforaphene compound, only 30 % corresponded to its nitrile form, which is
381 biologically inactive. While the nitrile form was not affected by the germination, the
382 sulforaphene was increased 26-fold compared to the seeds content (Table 4).

383 CTRL radish sprouts reported 2.65 g kg⁻¹ dw of sulforaphene at harvest. However, the
384 first application of UVC and UVB increased by 57 and 72 %, respectively, the
385 sulforaphene content regarding CTRL. In contrast, after the second UVC+B application,
386 the sulforaphene content increased by 38 % compared to CTRL (day 1). Also, the UVB
387 and UVC+B treatments in radish sprouts kept in a similar amount the sulforaphene
388 content throughout the storage period at 4 °C.

389 **4. DISCUSSION**

390 According to our results, a higher dry biomass has been previously related to the increased
391 content in bioactive compounds in *Brassicaceae* sprouts (Šamec et al., 2018).

392 Regarding the microbial load, it was maintained quite constant throughout the refrigerated
393 period without differences. This tendency was also observed by Castillejo et al. (2021)
394 reporting higher microbial counts.

395 After the analysis of the epiphytic microflora growth throughout shelf-life, it was
396 concluded that the UV doses used were enough to prevent the exponentially increase of
397 the microbial growth while not inducing any UV damage to the tissues. Furthermore,
398 UVC illumination is mainly used in sanitation due to the high germicidal properties of
399 this UV radiation, being considered as a sustainable alternative to conventional chemical
400 treatments. Accordingly, UV-C doses applied on day 0 and 1 of the refrigerated storage
401 period at 4 °C reduced the microbial load (mesophilic, psychophilic, enterobacteria,
402 moulds, and yeast) by approximately 0.5 and 1 log CFU g⁻¹ fw compared to CTRL sprouts

403 in both cruciferous species, which was only observed immediately after UV treatment.
404 The simultaneously application of UVC and UVB also reduced the microbial load of
405 mesophilic and moulds and yeasts by 0.5 log CFU g⁻¹ fw in comparison with CTRL
406 sprouts on application days. In fact, it is remarkable that there was not found a synergic
407 effect in psychrophilic and enterobacteria load when UVC and UVB were jointly applied.
408 In this way, although this reduction was specific after the treatment and it was not
409 maintained throughout the shelf-life study, our results agree with those previously
410 reported in fresh-cut carrots using the same UV doses by Formica-Oliveira et al. (2017a).
411 As presumed, UVB did not show any germicidal ability when applied alone.

412 From a general point of view, the TPC increased after UVC and UVC+B treatments on
413 minimally processed broccoli and radish sprouts, respectively, which can be due to the
414 better extraction of phenolic compounds after plant cells disruption provoked by UV. In
415 fact, such increase of phenolic content is a directly response to the application of
416 postharvest abiotic stresses like radiation (Cisneros-Zevallos 2003). The phenol
417 biosynthesis has been linked to the phenylalanine ammonia lyase (PAL) activation after
418 abiotic stresses caused by reactive oxygen species (ROS) as signalling substances
419 (Cisneros-Zevallos and Jacobo-Velázquez, 2020). In this way, phenolics, as absorber
420 compounds, are accumulated in the vacuoles of epidermal cells in response to UV lighting
421 and decrease the penetration of the radiation into deeper cell layers (Avena-Bustillos et
422 al., 2012).

423 Furthermore, UVC treatment also reported significant increases in broccoli sprouts after
424 treatments on day 0 and 1 and in radish sprouts on day 4. This results agree with recent
425 findings, which showed the enhancement of TPC after 7 d at 10 °C in acerola fruit treated
426 with 6 kJ m⁻² UV-C (Rabelo et al., 2020). Therefore, the abiotic stress induced by the UV
427 radiation, either by single or combination of UV-C and UV-B, have stimulated the

428 biosynthesis of phenolics by increasing the ROS production, which is able to activate the
429 key PAL enzyme.

430 Our TAC values agree with those previously reported by other authors, who measured
431 the TPC and TAC by DPPH of broccoli and radish sprouts (De la Fuente et al. 2019;
432 Pająk et al. 2014). In this sense, the TAC measured by DPPH was highly correlated to
433 TPC with $R^2 = 0.9620$ in broccoli sprouts and $R^2 = 0.8991$ in radish sprouts.

434 As previously discussed for TPC, the UV treatments also increased the TAC in the studied
435 samples, which may be due to a higher extraction of antioxidant compounds, such as,
436 phenolics. In fact, the TAC behaviour of samples during the refrigerated storage period
437 was similar to the TPC, since the biosynthesis of UV-absorbing compounds is the most
438 common way to fight against damaging caused by UV radiation (Nguyen et al., 2020).
439 Hence, secondary metabolites responsible of the TAC are accumulated in the surface cells
440 in response to these treatments. For this reason, minimally processed broccoli and radish
441 sprouts are considered an excellent ‘super food’, which antioxidant properties could be
442 even enhanced with a postharvest UV treatment, either UV-B, UV-C or combination.

443 Regarding glucosinolate content, broccoli sprouts are between 10 and 100-fold richer in
444 GLs in comparison with the adult plant (Pérez-Balibrea et al., 2011; Valente Pereira et
445 al., 2002).

446 The increase of the total GLs after UVB treatment, agree with previous authors findings,
447 which have also shown this behaviour in broccoli florets (Duarte-Sierra et al. 2020;
448 Formica-Oliveira et al. 2017b) and fresh-cut carrots (Formica-Oliveira et al. 2017a). In
449 addition, an amelioration effect of UV-B lighting during the preharvest period has been
450 also reported by several authors, regarding the biosynthesis of GLs in *Arabidopsis*
451 *thaliana* (Neugart et al., 2020) and broccoli sprouts (Moreira-Rodríguez et al., 2017a,

2017b). In fact, in response to UVB during the refrigerated storage, some genes are overexpressed to activate the GL pathway, such as the tryptophan N-hydroxylase (CYP79B3). This gene can be stimulated by 6-fold after low UVB doses and 10-fold after higher UVB doses (Duarte-Sierra et al., 2020). Besides, those high UV-B doses have been also able to overexpressed the dihomomethionine N-hydroxylase (CYP79F1) by 3-fold compared to control broccoli florets (Duarte-Sierra et al., 2020).

Furthermore, UVC sprouts reported similar results to UVC+B. Hence, that combination did not synergistically overexpress the GL biosynthesis. Our theory to explain this behaviour is that UV-B and UV-C could share the same photoreceptors in the plant. In fact, plants have at least five types of photoreceptors, which allow to perceive the light by themselves and trigger responses which prevent damage and optimize the development. As previously described, UVR8 protein has been described as the UV-B receptor, and its action spectrum also includes the UV-C region (Jiang et al., 2012), which suggests that they may share such receptor. This hypothesis can also explain why low doses of UV-C can stimulate phenolic compounds biosynthesis among other phytochemicals (Abdipour et al., 2019; Artés-Hernández et al., 2010; M. C. Rabelo et al., 2020). This can be explained with the fact that UV-C produces similar effects to UV-B or that the energy provided by shorter wavelengths of UV-C may block the UVR8, as main UV-B receptors.

As glucoraphanin level in broccoli sprouts is largely determined by genotype and the environment in which the plants are grown (e.g., location, year, drought, pollution, and disease pressure), and it is also higher in young plants compared to mature plants, also sulforaphane content has been found in large quantities in sprouts (Pérez-Balibrea et al., 2011; Valente Pereira et al., 2002; Yagishita et al., 2019). Williams et al., (2008) demonstrated that ESP is responsible for producing more inactive nitrile products than

477 bioactive product during GL hydrolysis in broccoli. Furthermore, ESP activity is highest
478 in seeds and decline steadily to lower levels in mature plants. In fact, the germination of
479 broccoli seeds had no effect on the sulforaphane content.

480 The content of sulforaphene nitrile in radish sprouts of the present study was lower than
481 the biologically active compound, sulforaphene. Wang et al. (2017) observed ESP gene
482 did not shown detectable expression in any organ in radish, while NSP5 gene had not
483 expression in the roots, but a minimal expression was found in other organs. As a matter
484 of fact, the 6 % of the glucoraphenin compound was converted into sulforaphene in radish
485 sprouts. Others authors have reported the higher specific activity of myrosinase in radish
486 (Yi et al., 2016), which positively affects to the converting ratio to ITCs from GLs in
487 comparison with broccoli. However, these low percentages corroborate the fact that some
488 GLs are metabolized into compounds that do not contribute to the evaluation of total ITCs
489 (Hanlon and Barnes, 2011). Even so, high GL content and the higher converting ratio
490 make UVB treated radish sprouts a preferable source of sulforaphene instead of broccoli
491 sprouts due to report up to 60-fold higher content. In fact, following the recommendations
492 of 100 μ M sulforaphane daily dose for healthy consumers provided by Egner et al. (2014)
493 and Riedl, Saxon, and Diaz-Sanchez (2009), an intake of 30 g of fresh UVB radish sprouts
494 per day can be proposed to enhance the detoxication of some airborne pollutants (Egner
495 et al., 2014) and to potent an increase in antioxidant Phase II enzymes in airway cells
496 (Riedl et al., 2009). Similarly, a consumption of 140 g of fresh UVB radish sprouts per
497 day (500 μ M SFN daily dose) may help to improve chemotherapy treatment in pancreatic
498 cancer patients (Lozanovski et al., 2014).

499 **5. CONCLUSIONS**

500 From a general point of view, a postharvest abiotic stress with UV illumination in both
501 *Brassicaceae* species showed an amelioration effect on the biosynthesis kinetics of the
502 main bioactive compounds, which some of them are well maintained throughout a shelf-
503 life period. The TPC and TAC were increased by UVB. The UVB treatment increased by
504 ~30 % the GL content compared to CTRL, which were mostly aliphatic GLs in radish
505 and indolyl GLs in broccoli. The sulforaphane content was also improved by 37.5 % in
506 UVB-treated broccoli sprouts while the sulforaphene content was highly increased by 72
507 % in UVB-treated radish sprouts. UVC and the combined application of UVC+B reported
508 similar contents of TAC, TPC and total GL content. This effect may be due to the fact
509 that UV-B and UV-C share the same photoreceptors in the plant and that UV-C saturates
510 UVR8 preventing the transcription of some genes that activate the biosynthesis of
511 bioactive compounds against abiotic stresses, as occurred when illuminating sprouts with
512 low UVB doses. Nevertheless, further research is needed to confirm our hypothesis. In
513 conclusion, UVB radish sprouts reported 5-fold more GLs and 60-fold more biologically
514 active ITCs content than broccoli sprouts. Therefore, we recommend the inclusion in the
515 consumers daily diet of *Brassicaceae* sprouts treated by UV radiation, which enhances
516 the concentration of potentially anti-inflammatory, anticarcinogenic, and antioxidant
517 bioactive compounds, for the prevention of chronic inflammatory diseases.

518 **DECLARATIONS**

519 **Author contributions statement**

520 Lorena Martínez-Zamora: Data curation; Formal analysis; Performed the experiments;
521 Investigation; Methodology; Writing - original draft. Noelia Castillejo: Data curation;
522 Formal analysis; Performed the experiments; Investigation; Methodology; Writing -
523 original draft. Francisco Artés-Hernández: Conceptualization; Funding acquisition;

524 Investigation; Project administration; Resources; Supervision; Validation; Visualization;
525 Writing - review & editing.

526 **Funding statement**

527 Project financed by the Autonomous Community of the Region of Murcia n° 20849/PI/18
528 through the grant call for projects for the development of scientific and technical research
529 by competitive groups, included in the Regional Programme for the Promotion of
530 Scientific and Technical Research (Action Plan 2018) of the Seneca Foundation - Science
531 and Technology Agency of the Region of Murcia (Spain).

532 **Acknowledgements**

533 Noelia Castillejo was funded by a predoctoral grant (FPU16/04763) from the Spanish
534 Ministry of Education. Lorena Martínez-Zamora contract has been co-financed by the
535 European Social Fund (ESF) and the Youth European Initiative (YEI) under the Spanish
536 Seneca Foundation (21322/PDGI/19). The technical assistance of Francisca Andreo is
537 highly appreciated.

538 **Competing interest statement**

539 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: